

Evaluating the Feasibility of using Soil-Moisture Active Passive Satellite Data to Evaluate Resilience of Transportation Infrastructures

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ABSTRACT

Soil-Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) satellite measures the water content in the top 5 cm (2 inches) of soil everywhere on the Earth's surface. SMAP launched in January 2015 and will collect observations for a three-year period (2015-2018), with a 2-3 day temporal resolution. It produces global soil moisture maps that can be used to improve the understanding of water and carbon cycle, improving weather forecasts, monitoring droughts, and predicting floods. These radar observations could also be superimposed on a map of transportation infrastructures to evaluate their resilience to extreme weather events. This project involved a multidisciplinary approach to managing flood risk to transportation infrastructures. The objectives of this study were to use remote sensing technology to improve the durability and lifespan of transportation infrastructures as well as improve flood predictions to prevent hazardous flooding.

INTRODUCTION

Flood events are the most severe natural disasters in the United States, causing significant property damages and potential loss of life. A series of conditions contribute towards a flooding event including antecedent moisture conditions, water table levels, above average precipitation events (Alsdorf et al., 2007; Hossain and Lettenmaier, 2006), as well as fluctuations in precipitation frequency and duration (NWS, 2005). As the water table levels rise, the storage deficit in the region decreases, which allows less water to infiltrate the subsurface. Soil saturation is arguably the most crucial variable in predicting flood events (Reager and Famiglietti, 2009, Rodell and Famiglietti, 1999). Reasonable estimations of real-time soil moisture and can be used to monitor a flood as it develops and help us understand the hydrologic conditions that lead to the most severe types.

Floods in urbanized regions of the United States drastically affect transportation infrastructures, including roads and pavements, and stormwater systems. Schwartz et al. (2014) found that climate change is an important driver that will impose additional costs on the nation's transportation infrastructure and their users. Road and pavement structures are critical components of communities and any damage to these structures could risk the access routes for maintenance and emergency services during a flood event and cause more frequent construction, maintenance and rehabilitation costs post-flood.

BACKGROUND

The road pavement system is in continuous interaction with its environment. While designing pavement systems, different environmental conditions must be considered. The new Mechanistic-Empirical Pavement Design Guide (MEPDG) incorporates the environmental factors as an Enhanced Integrated Climate Model (EICM). The EICM simulates the impact of environmental conditions on pavement characteristics and properties. The Federal Highway Administration (FHWA) developed the initial EICM and was later implemented in the pavement design guide (Witczak et al., 2004). It consists of three major components:

- infiltration and drainage model
- climatic-materials-structural model
- frost heave and thaw settlement model

One of the most relevant components of EICM in the evaluation of pavement systems and transportation infrastructure in coastal areas is the impact of moisture content. The design guide for new pavement structures recommends the placement and compaction of pavement layers at or near the optimum moisture conditions. The optimum moisture content of geomaterials occurs at the maximum dry density in laboratory conditions. However, any variation in moisture content from optimum conditions would lead to a lower dry density of compacted geomaterials. The variation of moisture content in pavement materials are categorized as follows (Zapata and Houston, 2008):

- variation of moisture content from initial or optimum value to the equilibrium condition
- seasonal variation of moisture content that could happen due to precipitation, flash storms, sea level rise and groundwater table rise
- variation of moisture content due to freeze/thaw cycles during cold seasons

The primary reason to study the moisture variation in pavement systems is the effect of moisture on the strength of pavement geomaterials regarding the resilient modulus (MR) and stiffness. Increasing moisture content in compacted geomaterial layers result in a reduction of MR and stiffness. An excessive amount of water in pavement structure could lead to reduced structural performance and load bearing capacity of the pavement system. This scenario is more likely to happen during or after extreme weather events such as flash floods, sea level rise and storm surges. Evaluating the short term and long term structural capacity of pavement structure during and after weather events could help decision makers decide when to resume traffic on a flooded section of

a highway. Furthermore, consideration of these fluctuations during the design process could also improve the durability of pavement structure susceptible to extreme weather events.

The following sections include the process to evaluate the impact of an extreme weather event on soil moisture level and estimate the loss of strength in road foundation layers due to inundation and flood using satellite data.

METHODOLOGY

The main objective of this study was to use remote sensing and satellite data for a recent major hurricane event to evaluate the risk of flooding and inundation to the major transportation infrastructures within the study area. The following sections discuss the extents of the study area, extraction of satellite data and the results of preliminary investigations. An extended version of such methodology is favorable for local stakeholder, state highway agencies and departments of transportation (DOTs) in coastal regions that are prone to the extreme weather events.

Study Area

This study focused on evaluating transportation infrastructure resilience due to water intrusion within the greater Houston, Texas region. In August 2017, the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Association's (NOAA) National Hurricane Center issued a storm-surge warning to Texas stating there will be an onset of torrential rainfall, and life-threatening danger due to inundation (NOAA, 2017). Soon after, the tropical storm warning changed to a Category 4 hurricane, referred to as Hurricane Harvey. Hurricane Harvey lasted approximately ten days and resulted in a staggering 100-160 centimeters of rainfall in several parts of Texas causing inundation of some major transportation infrastructures (Figure 1). The time-frame considered for this study is from August 17, 2017, to September 3, 2017, to evaluate the impact of Hurricane Harvey.

Figure 1 – Flooding on Interstate Highway 10 in Houston, TX (Photo: Brett Coomer, Houston Chronicle)

Storm Surge Prediction

National Oceanic and Atmospheric Association’s (NOAA) has developed a tool to illustrate and visualize the affected areas by storm surge at different severity levels. These predictions were categorized by hurricane categories, also known as Saffir-Simpson hurricane scale, as explained in Table 1 (Saffir and Simpson, 1995).

Table 1 – Characteristics of different Hurricane categories

	Category 1	Category 2	Category 3	Category 4	Category 5
Wind Speed (mph)	74-95	96-110	111-129	130-156	> 157
Storm Surge (ft)	4-5	6-8	9-12	13-18	> 18
Damage Level	Minimal	Moderate	Extensive	Extreme	Catastrophic

The visualization tool shows the inundation height at different geographical locations under different hurricane categories. The storm surge caused inundation over several highways and roads in Houston, Texas. Figure 2 illustrates the affected areas and prediction of inundation heights for hurricane categories 1 through 5. For category 1, inundation occurs on most coastal highways and roads, with the predicted depth of about 3 ft. As the hurricane become stronger and turns to category 2, most of the low-lying areas on the south-eastern part of the area becomes inundated with a predicted height of water about 6 ft above ground. For the most extreme scenario, hurricane category 5, significant parts of Interstate 10 and 45 become inundated with the predicted height of water about 9 ft above ground. Such inundation events will interrupt the major access roads and blocks the evacuation routes. Not only will the flooded sections of the highway interrupt the flow of traffic, but the foundation layer of inundated roads will become more susceptible to damage.

The following sections include evaluation of flooding from different sources of moisture intrusion into road and pavement structure using satellite data.

Remote Sensing Datasets

Figure 3 illustrates the sources of water intrusion in road structures and pavement layers. Several datasets are used to obtain a holistic perspective of the water intrusion onto transportation infrastructure. We downloaded these products from the NASA Goddard Earth Sciences Data and Information Services Center (GES DISC), a freely available dataset for the community. The datasets are described in subsequent sections below; all datasets extracted were evaluated directly over the Houston, TX region contained within the dimensions of a bounding box as summarized in Table 2. The following section summarizes the datasets from each of these satellite data.

Table 2 - Geographical extents of the extracted satellite data

Extents (Decimal Coordinates)	From	To
Latitude	31.1133 N	28.7402 N
Longitude	97.0093 W	93.9771 W

Figure 2 – Category 1 through 5 storm inundation and the impact on the transportation network (NOAA, 2016)

Figure 3 - Sources of water intrusion to the pavement structure from Christopher et al. (2006) and how they are estimated using NASA Products

Volumetric soil moisture on the surface

NASA's Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) sensor measures the near-surface soil moisture (0-5 cm depth) everywhere on Earth's surface (Panciera et al., 2014). It produces global soil moisture maps [in m^3/m^3] at the 9 km spatial and 24-hour temporal resolution that are used to predict surface soil moisture.

Water Storage

Water table depth can be estimated using NASA's Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment (GRACE). GRACE provides a groundwater storage percentile, or percentage of storage filled. As the subsurface fills, the groundwater storage reaches 100%. GRACE has been previously used to assess regional flood potential (Reager et al., 2015). The GRACE satellite takes measurements at a 0.125-degree spatial resolution on a 7-day time interval. The GRACE sensor also provides an estimate of percent soil moisture or percent of subsurface pore-space filled with water within the top 5 cm. GRACE observations in this study were extracted for the period of July 31, 2017, to August 28, 2017, because the more recent products need to be processed by NASA.

Precipitation

At the time of extraction, commonly used estimates of precipitation including Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM) and Global Precipitation Climatology Project (GPCP) were unavailable. To develop an estimation of total precipitation during this time frame, the North American Land Data Assimilation Product (NLDAS-2), that provides a 1/8 degree spatial resolution, and hourly temporal resolution in mmhr^{-1} , was evaluated (Xia et al., 2009). The hourly resolution was aggregated to daily by summing the total hourly precipitation.

Surface water inundation

Surface water accumulation on a road infrastructure can be incredibly hazardous to users due to safety risks, and further could reduce the strength of pavement foundation layer causing short- and long-term surface deterioration and deformation. Several studies have developed methods to evaluate surface water inundation using passive and active sensors. Kwak et al. (2014) developed an algorithm to determine flood risk using Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (MODIS), and a digital elevation model. They reported that this approach was feasible for detection of instant inundation. MODIS provides daily optical images at a spatial resolution that ranges depending on the wavelength band including 250, 500, and 1000 m. This study focuses on determining inundation of all paved highway surfaces. Lopez and Maxwell (2015) developed a method using Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) observations to detect a paved or unpaved surface as a function of reflectivity.

PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Figure 4 illustrates the area-averaged total daily precipitation overlaying the soil moisture data from SMAP satellite within the Houston bounding box. The yellow shaded region highlights the Hurricane Harvey time-frame. The hurricane resulted in unprecedented precipitation totals where precipitation peaked at 175 cm on August 27th and remained relatively high until August 29th resulting in an increase in soil moisture on the surface (Figure 3b). We observe that as the hyetograph increased due to the storm, volumetric soil moisture within the area rose substantially from 0.2 m³/m³ to 0.45 m³/m³. The area-averaged soil moisture value on August 29th was 0.425 m³/m³. Soil moisture variability was narrow around this time frame indicating most observational cells within the bounding box were similar and of a high measurement. Post-hurricane soil moisture receded until September 17th, which reflects another smaller intensity storm period.

Figure 5 provides the SMAP swath area estimated over the United States (left inset), and an expanded view of the soil moisture within the Houston area bounding box. The soil moisture measurements within the Midwest region represented lower bounds of the measurement spectrum ranging from 0.0 m³/m³ to 0.3 m³/m³. The region, directly impacted by the hurricane, experienced higher soil moisture measurements, especially around the coastline.

Seven-day observations from GRACE satellite, provided from July 31st to August 27th, indicate that soil moisture was increasing due to the storms preceding the hurricane (as shown in Figure 6), rising from 38% to 92%. Soil moisture slightly declined to 78% before the storm. However, the soil surface was unable to recover before being inundated with record high precipitation. The percent groundwater storage also demonstrates this trend. As data becomes more readily available from satellites, these analyses could be further improved and expanded.

Figure 4 – Area-averaged total daily precipitation overlaying the soil moisture within the Houston bounding box

Figure 5 - Temporal SMAP data on August 29th, 2017 for a) the USA and b) Houston

Figure 6 - GRACE time-series for groundwater storage (blue curve) and soil moisture (black curve) in percent

Effect of Moisture Variation on the Strength of Pavement Foundation

The modulus of compacted pavement foundation layers is affected by different factors including the state of stress, moisture content, density, gradation, plasticity, and the long-term and short-term behavior of materials (Mazari et al. 2013). Some studies have been dedicated to investigating the impact of moisture content or degree of saturation on the stiffness of soils and unbound foundation layers (Nazarian et al. 2014, Mazari et al. 2015, Cary and Zapata 2010, Sotelo et al. 2014). The modulus (stiffness) of a compacted unbound pavement foundation layers, which is the indicator of materials strength under traffic loads, usually decreases when the moisture content increases (Pacheco & Nazarian, 2011; Khoury & Zaman, 2004).

Witczak et al. (2000), as part of the development of the mechanistic-empirical pavement design guide (MEPDG), proposed Eq. 1 to accommodate the effect of moisture as a function of the degree of saturation on modulus:

$$\log\left(\frac{M_R}{M_{Ropt}}\right) = a + \frac{b-a}{1+e^{\left(\frac{\ln\frac{b}{a}+k_m \times (S-S_{opt})}{a}\right)}} \quad (1)$$

where M_R = modulus at a degree of saturation S ; M_{Ropt} = modulus at the maximum dry density and optimum moisture content (the pavement foundation layers are ideally constructed under these conditions); S_{opt} = degree of saturation at the maximum dry density and optimum moisture content; a = minimum of $\log(M_R/M_{Ropt})$ (-0.3123 and -0.5934 for coarse- and fine-grained materials, respectively); b = maximum of $\log(M_R/M_{Ropt})$ (0.3010 and 0.3979 for coarse- and fine-grained materials, respectively); k_m = regression parameter (6.8157 and 6.1324 for coarse- and fine-grained materials, respectively).

This model shows that for a 30 percent increase in the degree of saturation of the fine-grained soil layer, the modulus of compacted pavement foundation layer could decrease by about 50 percent. Consequently, the load-bearing capacity of the pavement system will reduce dramatically.

However, the satellite data in Figure 6 estimated that the soil moisture in the area increased by about 70 percent during the hurricane period. This increase in soil moisture could have caused a significant decline in the strength of transportation infrastructure foundation layers during inundation times. It should be noted that a more detailed investigation of soil saturation condition from groundwater information using GRACE satellite data will be needed to extend the analysis for future studies.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This study included a preliminary investigation of using remotely sensed satellite data to estimate the soil moisture and groundwater levels during a major hurricane event. The variation of moisture data was extracted from satellite information. The moisture variations were partially used to provide an approximate appraisal of transportation infrastructure foundation layers. It should be noted that this study only reflects a preliminary phase of the analysis and more detailed process need to be performed to correlate satellite data with in-situ field measurements. The following conclusions were drawn from this study:

- Surface saturation levels are a function of soil moisture and surface porosity. In order to obtain a high-resolution estimation of surface saturation that improves on the GRACE estimates, the surface properties within the Houston bounding box is required.
- Surface properties include land cover and soil type. The surface saturation can be calculated at each pixel by estimating the surface porosity within that pixel.
- The final portion of the hydrologic perspective is deriving the inundation levels using the MODIS products described in the methodology section.

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